

NEW RESTORATIONS OF ENESCU'S WORK

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3597227

Summary

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After a similar previous research (see the journal *Art, Audiovisual Arts*, 2017), the article takes a look at a series of early works by George Enescu: the lyric scene *La vision de Saul*, 1895, *Ouverture tragique*, 1895, *Ouverture triomphale*, 1896, the cantata *Laurore*, 1898, the oratory *Ahasverus*, 1895, *Fantaisie* for piano and orchestra, 1898.

The literary sources of the adolescent opposites, the architectural and writing particularities, the poles of stylistic attraction towards which he gravitates are analyzed.

The author wants to highlight the efforts of the musicians, thanks to whom George Enescu's "school" compositions have been brought back to the concert stage and played to today's music-loving audience. Flaviu Mogoșan, Gabriel Bebeșelea, Ciprian Gabriel Pop are among them. Cluj interpreters, those from the Opera and those from the Philharmonic, were also actively involved in the restitutions of Enescu.

The journey through the creation of the young Enescu shows us a composer in full formation, with an impeccable technique in the construction and orchestration, with a remarkable symphonic instinct and an innate dramatic sense.

Key words: George Enescu, early creation, stylistic attraction poles, remarkable symphonic instinct, innate dramatic sense, reconstruction after sketches, reconstruction after tempo, performance in concert.

Rezumat

Noi restituiri enesciene

După o incursiune similară anterioară (a se vedea *Arta, Arte audiovizuale*, 2017), articolul ia în vizor un șir de lucrări timpurii ale lui George Enescu: scena lirică *La vision de Saul*, 1895, *Ouverture tragique*, 1895, *Ouverture triomphale*, 1896, cantata *Laurore*, 1898, oratoriul *Ahasverus*, 1895, *Fantaisie* pentru pian și orchestră, 1898.

Sunt analizate sursele literare ale opusurilor adolescente, particularitățile arhitectonice și de scriitură, poliile de atracție stilistică spre care gravitează.

Autorul ține să pună în valoare efortul muzicienilor, grație cărora compozițiile „de școală” ale lui George Enescu au fost readuse în scena de concert și redat publicului meloman de astăzi. Printre aceștia se numără Flaviu Mogoșan, Gabriel Bebeșelea, Ciprian Gabriel Pop. În restituirile enesciene s-au implicat activ și interpreții clujeni, cei de la Operă și cei de la Filarmonică.

Periplul prin creația tânărului Enescu ne arată un compozitor în plină formare, cu o tehnică impecabilă la nivelul construcției și orchestrației, cu un remarcabil instinct simfonic și cu un simț dramatic înăscut.

Cuvinte-cheie: George Enescu, creație timpurie, poliile de atracție stilistică, remarcabil instinct simfonic, simț dramatic înăscut, reconstituire după schițe, reconstituire după știme, interpretare în concert.

Recent first auditions at the Transylvania Philharmonic and the National Opera in Cluj have revealed new facets of Enescu's teenage composition progress.

The lyrical scene *La vision de Saül* is written during the studies with Jules Massenet in Paris and bears the date of June 19, 1895, when the author was not yet 14 years old.

Massenet appreciates the work, which proves "symphonic instinct, unity and great authenticity from a dramatic point of view".

The work is made up of an orchestral prelude and five scenes, with three soloists (Saul, David

and Michal), being supported from the pit and the backstage.

From a stylistic point of view it oscillates between Wagnerian influences and French lyricism. Symphonic character, expressive vocal writing, dramatic culminations are found in this biblical scene, written by a common writer, Eugène-Felix Ademis, who was probably inspired by the drama of Voltaire. It is a text that was proposed to the Rome Prize candidates in 1896.

Later, young Debussy will win the prize, also with a vocal-symphonic work.

The effort of the Cluj Opera deserves appreciation, as it presented the work in concert, with the substantial contribution of conductor Gh. Victor Dumănescu and soloists Cristian Hodrea, Cristian Mogoșan and Irina Săndulescu Balan.

The score, the parts and the piano excerpts were excellently made by Flaviu Mogosan, after the original manuscript, extremely readable. The backstage orchestra was pre-recorded, so the score could be performed according to the author's will.

We consider that young Enescu proved an amazing dramatic sense in this ample work of about 30 minutes, warmly received by the public in April 2019.

Another area of great interest is the concert of the Cluj-Napoca Philharmonic on December 7, which presented in the first absolute audition no less than five works directed by Gabriel Bebeșelea.

The concert began with two concert overtures, Overture tragique op.6 and Overture triomphale op.11, composed at 14 and 15 years old respectively.

The numbering of the "school" opuses (Saul had op.2) shows us a composer in full formation with an impeccable compositional technique at the level of construction and orchestration.

Here too, the stylistic influences lean towards Brahms, the Viennese influence being more visible than the Parisian one.

The first part of the concert ended with a fragment from the "Strigoi" (The Ghosts) oratorio (1916), already a mature work, in the interpretation of tenor Tiberius Simu (Avald's monologue from the first part of the Oratorio).

We mention that Gabriel Bebeșelea recorded a CD of great prestige (Capriccio Viena) with the Berlin Radio Orchestra, following the concert presentation of the Oratorio on September 26 in Berlin, with the same orchestra.

The reconstruction of the manuscript (piano voices) was done in the 1970s and the orchestration belongs to Sabin Păutza.

The second part included a short L'aurore cantata, soprano, women's choir and orchestra, finished in Paris on 8 January 1898 on the lyrics of the French poet Leconte de Lisle. It is a short cantata (about 7 minutes), with more mature stylistic coordinates, where the influence of the French school is largely felt.

Parnasian poet, Leconte de Lisle (1818-1894) reprises here also the great myths of Oriental civilization.

It was of great interest the first audition of Ahasvèrus op.5 (first part), written immediately after Saul in the autumn of 1895, on the Libretto written in 1892 by French playwright Lucien Augé de Lassus.

The first three scenes, blasphemy, pleasure and love are dated as follows:

— the first scene *Le blasphème*, September 28, 1895

— scene II is entirely orchestrated

— scene III, *L'Amour*, is partially orchestrated, without a final date.

Gabriel Bebeșelea drafted the two overtures and the cantata *L'Aurore*, also finishing the orchestration of the third painting from Ahasvèrus after the sketches found at the Enescu Museum.

This first part is a visible leap after Saul. Composer Charles Koechlin writes in the article in the musical magazine *Le Ménestrel* (March 22, 1935) *Souvenirs from Massenet classes*: "1er tableau d'Ahasvèrus d'Enesco, Etonnant Comme développement, sit beaucoup plus modern d'harmonies que musique de l'an dernier". (First painting by Ahasvèrus de Enescu. Amazing as development and much more modern in harmony than his last year music).

Octavian Lazar Cosma also studied this manuscript at the Enescu Museum. He notes: "Even from the orchestral introduction, the sober, merciless atmosphere of the future action is drawn through the violoncello theme, preaching intonational formulas so common in Enescu's works. In Ahasvèrus, as opposed to other lyrical attempts, in the musical discourse, the choir's interventions, the pathetic, in the first painting and lyrical in the second, have an important role."

This first part is written for soloists, mixed choir and orchestra, with Diana Țugui, Tiberius Simu, Michael Mrozek, Ruben Ciungan, Sándor Kőpeczi and the Philharmonic choir conducted by Cornel Groza, with a duration of approximately 30 minutes.

It is a significant moment in young Enescu's creation. After Saul, Ahasvèrus, and later the Ghosts (Strigoi) are mere accumulations for Oedipus.

It is clear that it would have not been born without these prior accumulations, which show us to what extent its preparation relies on the experiences previously acquired.

Among these, Ahasvèrus, through the drama of the first part and the lyricism of the next parts, represents a point of support for future developments.

The score also has short directions, which show that the author also considered a stage version, including intermingling of dancing moments, etc.

And one last restoration: *Fantaisie* for piano and orchestra, written in 1898 and performed in the first (and only) audition on April 8, 1900 in Bucharest and conducted by the author himself at the Romanian Athenaeum, with the solo pianist Theodor Fuchs, to whom he dedicated his work. It will also be performed at the “Gheorghe Dima” Music Academy in Cluj in November. The score parts found at the Enescu Museum allowed for the reconstruction of the lost score by composer Ciprian

Gabriel Pop, to whom we give our thanks here.

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The image shows a handwritten musical score for the piece "Ahasvéus. Prologue. Le Gasphème." The title is written in a large, elegant cursive script at the top. Below the title, the tempo marking "Allegro" is written. The score is arranged in a standard orchestral format with multiple staves. The instruments listed on the left include: Flute (Flûte), Oboe (2 Flûtes), Clarinet (2 Clarinettes en si b), Bassoon (2 Bassons), Horns (Corns en fa, I and II), Trumpets (2 Trompettes en fa), Timpani (3 Timbales en fa, si, mi), Drum (Caisse), Violins (Violons, I and II), Viola (Vielle), and Cello/Double Bass (C.-Basse). The score features various musical notations, including notes, rests, and dynamic markings such as "pp".